

**EFFECT OF VIDHHAKARMA IN HYSTERIA & DISCONSTRAINT PSYCHOPATHIC
PERSONALITY WITH VISHADA (CHRONIC DEPRESSION)****Dr. Adinath E. Nagre BAMS***

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ABSTRACT

A healthy mind in a healthy body is a component of absolute health. In its definition of health, Ayurveda emphasizes the significance of preserving mental clarity, the sense organs, and the body's regular physiological processes. Ayu (life), which represents the idea of psychosomatic in Ayurveda, is a combination of *Shareera*, *Indriya*, *Satwa*, and *Atma*. WHO states, "Health is a complete physical, mental, and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. Ayurveda gives prime importance to positive mental health. Anything that disturbs the balance of body and mind is known to produce a disease. In Ayurveda, more importance is given to the mental health of the *rogi*. *Vishada* means Sadness or fear which *Rajasa* and *Tamasa doshas* are increased. *Lakshanas* of *Vishada* in ayurveda can be *Kayika*, *Vachika*, and *Manasika lakshanas*. It is caused by the vitiation of *Vata (Sharirika dosha)* and *Raja (Manasika dosha)*. Depression is not simply the same as feeling sad. While it is normal to experience low mood or a lack of motivation occasionally, depression is more persistent and long-lasting. It is a serious mood disorder that can significantly affect overall health, quality of life, and even the well-being of those around the individual. A 41-year-old female patient, diagnosed by a psychiatrist with hypomania, hysteria, and a disconstraint psychopathic personality, was managed through *Vidhhakarma* and *shamana chikitsa*. By the end of the treatment, notable improvement was observed in both subjective and objective parameters. The patient became cheerful and actively engaged in her daily activities. Her Hamilton Depression Scale score significantly reduced from 27 to 1, and her pre-existing allopathic medications were gradually tapered off during treatment and - subsequent follow-ups. This case shows that Ayurveda, when addressing the body, mind, and social well-being, can help provide lasting relief from depression.

KEYWORDS: Hysteria, Vishada, Vidhhakarama, Depression.**INTRODUCTION**

Hysteria is undoubtedly the first mental disorder attributable to women, accurately described in the second millennium BC, and until Freud considered an exclusively female disease. Hysteria is a term used to mean ungovernable emotional excess and can refer to a temporary state of mind or emotion.^[1] In the nineteenth century, female hysteria was considered a diagnosable physical illness in women.^[2]

Depression is a serious mental health condition which affects around 300 million people worldwide. It is a common mental disorder presented with depressed mood, loss of interest or pleasure, feeling guilty, disturbed sleep and low power of concentration.^[3] Its prevalent mental health condition, affecting around 5% of the general population and 10– 20% of individuals with chronic medical illnesses.^[4] Clinical features may vary from mild symptoms such as sadness, anxiety, irritability, worry, poor concentration, discouragement,

and physical complaints to more severe forms of clinical depression.^[5] A depressive episode is characterized by a persistently low mood or a marked loss of interest and pleasure in daily activities, lasting for most of the day, nearly every day, for a minimum of two weeks.^[6] The disorder presents with a combination of psychological as well as somatic symptoms.

In Ayurveda, Charaka has mentioned that *Satva*, *Atma* and *Sharira* are the *Tridanda* (Pillars) of the body. He has explained that *Sharira* and *Mana* serves as a site for manifestation of diseases or *Vedana* while *Atma* is essentially devoid of all the pathogenicity and it is detached from all the bodily or psychological ailments. All the *Sharirika Rogas* are not evolved without *Vata*, *Pitta* and *Kapha*, similarly for *Manasika Vikara*, it always occurs due to an imbalance of *Satva*, *Rajas* and *Tamas*. It can be correlated with conditions such as *Vishada* (sadness), *Avasada* (exhaustion), and *Kaphaja Unmada*. Primary psychological states influenced by *Manasa*

Dosha include *Rajas* and *Tamas*, which give rise to emotions and mental states such as *Kama* (lust), *Krodha* (anger), *Lobha* (greed), *Moha* (delusion), *Irshya* (jealousy), *Mada* (euphoria), *Shoka* (grief), *Chinta* (anxiety), *Udvega* (neurosis), and *Bhaya* (fear). Many of these correspond with the symptoms seen in depression. According to Ayurveda, the key pathogenic factors in depression are hyperactivity of *Tamo Guna* and imbalance of *Rajo Guna*. At the physical level, depression is marked by vitiation of *Kapha Dosha* and depletion of *Vata Dosha*. Depression is often managed with electroconvulsive therapy, mood stabilizers, and antidepressants. Although these treatments can be effective to some extent, they are frequently associated with side effects and drug interactions. This highlights the need for safe and natural approaches to managing depression in order to reduce potential long-term complications. Ayurveda recommends effective *Vidhakarman* mentioned in selective clinical condition where *Vata Dushti* presents. Along with these, *Shamana Chikitsa* (internal medicine) also emphasizes the role of yoga and meditation in the management of depression. This procedure release vitiated *Vata* in affected area. *Vidhakarman* is also known as *Vedhana*. It is one of eight *Shashtrakarma* mentioned in *Sushrut Samhita*.^[7] This is a sterile procedure which includes piercing points with special hollow needle considering the anatomy of *Marmas*. *Vidhakarman* doesn't require any internal medication as an addictive to enhance its effect.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

Aim of the present study was to evaluate the effect of *vidhakarman* in hysteria.

MATERIAL AND METHODS CASE HISTORY

A 41-year-old female patient was suffering from anger, irritability, loss of activities and energy, low mood, fatigue, loss of appetite, heaviness of head, swelling over foot, disturbed sleep from 10 years. She was a known case of depression for the past ten years and had been on regular psychiatric treatment. Her medications included: Tab. Sertima SO – for depression, Tab. Oxietrol-XR – anticonvulsant, Tab. Trinicalm Plus – prescribed for schizophrenia, Cap. Rejiyana – for nutritional and hormonal imbalance. The patient underwent treatment but did not experience significant relief. Over time, her symptoms worsened. In addition, she reported late initiation of sleep with frequent sleep fragmentation, marked reduction in appetite, and occasional episodes of irrational fear. After getting so many treatments when patient didn't get any significant relief then approached toward Ayurvedic management. When she came to OPD for advice, then on examination and after taking history and patient was found with maximum symptoms of *Vishada*. On assessment, her Hamilton Depression Rating Scale score was 27.

Clinical findings General examination

Temperature	97.6
RR	20/min
Pulse Rate	103/min
Blood Pressure	110/70 mm of hg
Height	158 cm
Height Weight	85 kg

Systemic Examination

RS	AEBE clear
CVS	S1S2 Normal
CNS	Conscious, oriented
P/A	Soft and non- tender

Ashtavidha Parikshana

Nadi	103/min (vataj)
Mala	Alpa badhham
Mutra	Samyak
Jivha	Sputik
Shabda	Spasht
Sparsha	Sheet
Druk	Prakrut
Akriti	Sthul

Dashavidha Parikshan

Prakruti	Vata-pitta
Vikruti	Vata and tama guna
Sarata	Astisarta
Samhanama	Madhyama
Satva	Alpasatvi
Vaya	41 yrs
Bala	Alpa
Satmya	Madhyama
Aahar shakti	Madhyama
Vayam shakti	Alpa

Vikrit Strotas Parikshan Strotas Parikshan WNL Except
Manovaha Strotasa: Chinta, Bhaya, Dwesha, Shoka
Rasavaha Strotasa: Mukhshosha
Annavaha Strotasa: Anannabhilasha, kshudha mandya
Medovaha Strotas: Prasweda
Purishvaha Strotasa: Asamyak Mala-Pravritti

Diagnostic criteria

According to *Charaka Samhita*, both physical and mental aspects can be understood through *Anumana Pariksha* (inference-based examination). These aspects are described under the concept of *Anumanajanya Bhava*. In light of this principle, the patient's condition was diagnosed as *Vishada* (depression) and the diagnostic criteria of *Vishada* by using the HAMILTON DEPRESSION SCALE ASSESSMENT Scores- 27.^[8]

Therapeutic intervention

The patient initially refused to take any oral medications and insisted on starting treatment only with *Vidhakarman* (needle-prick therapy). However, *Lakshmililas Rasa* was administered under compulsion at a dose of one tablet twice daily.

Site For Viddha Karma^[9] Sankha Marma

शङ्ख केशान्त संधीगतं उरोऽपाङ्गललाटेषु च उन्मादे ॥ सु.शा.8/17

उन्मादे शङ्खकेशान्तसंधधगतं, उरोऽपाङ्गललाट्ां च उन्मादे | वा. सु. 27

Lalata & Apanga sites

युरोआपंगललाटेषु धसराशचास्य धवमोक्षयेत् ॥”

(सुश्रुत उत्तरतन्त्र ६३/२४)

ललाटपाङ्गयां वा एता एव धशरोगाधीमान्धप्रभृदतषु रोगेषु इधता”

(सुश्रुत सधंिता, शारीरस्थान ८/१७)

Details of Viddhakarma^[10/11]

- Near Shankha Marma – depth of puncture: *half Vrihi*
- At Lalata (forehead) and Apanga (outer canthus of eye) points – depth of puncture: *1/4 Vrihi*
- Above Kshipra Marma (two finger breadths above) – depth of puncture: *full Vrihi*

Viddhakarma (therapeutic puncturing) was initiated four times a week on a regular basis.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

After vidhhakarma the changes in Hamilton's Depression Rating Scale are noted.

The initial score on HDRS of the patient before vidhhakarma was 27 and after the treatment it was 1. The scoring change was significant from Severe to Mild.

Hamilton's Depression Rating Scale

Symptoms	Pre-treatment	Post treatment
Depressed mood	3	0
Guilt feeling	4	0
Suicide	0	0
Insomnia- Early	2	0
Middle Late	1	0
	2	0
Work and Activities	3	0
Psychomotor retardation	3	1
Agitation	1	0
Anxiety – Somatic	1	0
Psychological	2	0
Somatic symptoms of GI	1	0
General	1	0
Hypochondriasis	2	0
Weight loss by history	0	0
Insight	1	0
Total score	27	1

Date	Observed Changes According to follow-up
15/04/2025 visit day	depression, lack of enthusiasm, feeling of guilt, helplessness, Lack of self-confidence, Inability to sleep, reduced digestive power and sensory strength, weakness, Bilateral foot, swelling all over the body, palpitation
02/05/2025	Sleep improved (stopped medicine) digestion is good, weakness reduced, palpitation reduced.
16/05/2025	Swelling totally reduced, confidence was good, physical & mental strength is improved. (all medicines reduced to half dose)
03/06/2025	Had misword with husband & feeling of guilt for few days, sleep also

	disturbed for few days (stopped all medicine continued half tab of OXIETROL –XR as tapering the dose)
22/06/2025	No complaints – attended a program with good confidence.
13/07/2025	Did Anchoring in program, after many years she presented herself

DISCUSSION

The present case highlights the clinical utility of Viddha Karma as an effective intervention for managing *Vishada* (chronic depression) and associated psychiatric manifestations such as hysteria and features of disconstraint psychopathic personality. The patient had a long history of depressive illness (10 years), resistant to conventional psychiatric medications, including antidepressants and antipsychotics. Despite prolonged pharmacological treatment, symptoms such as irritability, guilt feelings, insomnia, reduced appetite, psychomotor retardation, and social withdrawal persisted, indicating treatment resistance.

From an Ayurvedic perspective, the patient's condition was correlated with *Vishada*, a state of mental distress caused by the predominance of *Tamas* and *Rajas*, along with *Vata* vitiation. Classical Ayurvedic texts mention the involvement of *Manovaha Srotas* and disturbance in mental equilibrium due to imbalance in *Satva*, *Rajas*, and *Tamas*. In such conditions, Viddha Karma (therapeutic puncture), an ancient para surgical technique mentioned by Sushruta, is indicated for *Vata*-related disorders, including certain *Manasika Vikaras*.

Mechanistically, Viddha Karma acts by producing a controlled micro-trauma at *Marmasthanas* like *Shankha*, *Lalata*, and *Apanga*, which are closely linked to neurovascular structures. This stimulus is believed to modulate neurophysiological pathways, enhance endorphin release, and reduce sympathetic overactivity, thereby alleviating anxiety, agitation, and depressive features. The improvement in Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HDRS) score from 27 (severe) to 1 (normal) underscores the effectiveness of the intervention.

Additionally, the therapy demonstrated benefits such as, improvement in sleep quality without sedatives, restoration of digestive power and appetite, reduction of psychosomatic complaints like heaviness, swelling, and fatigue, enhancement of social confidence, as evidenced by the patient resuming public speaking and anchoring after many years.

This integrative approach using Viddha Karma with minimal oral medication (Lakshmvilas Rasa) also ensured safety, minimal invasiveness, and cost-effectiveness. Unlike modern psychiatric drugs that often cause side effects and dependency, this Ayurvedic intervention provided sustained relief without adverse effects.

CONCLUSION

This case illustrates that Viddha Karma, when performed at specific *Marmasthanas* such as *Shankha*, *Lalata*, and *Apanga*, can significantly reduce symptoms of *Vishada* (chronic depression) and associated psychiatric conditions like hysteria and psychopathic personality traits. The intervention facilitated holistic improvement by addressing both psychological and somatic symptoms, thereby reaffirming Ayurveda's emphasis on *Sharira–Mana–Atma* balance for mental health.

Given its simplicity, safety, and efficacy, Viddha Karma holds promise as an adjunct or alternative therapy for treatment-resistant psychiatric disorders. Nevertheless, larger-scale clinical trials and comparative studies with modern treatments are essential to validate its therapeutic role and standardize protocols for mental health care.

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